

DiSSCo Transition Project

Model of training resources for the DiSSCo Helpdesk

Work Package 2 - Deliverable 2.3

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Executive Summary

This report outlines a structured model for developing self-service resources as the first layer of support within the DiSSCo Helpdesk. Task 2.3, led by CETAF in collaboration with ULisboa and UoC, focuses on providing accessible, automated support for users of the DiSSCo Research Infrastructure (RI). A survey was conducted to assess user awareness of key DiSSCo tools (ELViS, CDD, DiSSCover, and DSR) and identify preferred support formats. Despite a low response rate, findings highlight the need for clear documentation, video tutorials, and FAQs to address common user challenges, including limited awareness of service functionalities, navigation difficulties, and uncertainty regarding data submission processes. Recommendations include structuring support resources based on user roles, centralising materials on dedicated help pages, and ensuring ongoing updates through collaboration between service providers and the helpdesk. AI-driven support features, such as chatbots, are also explored for their potential to enhance efficiency and multilingual accessibility, though human oversight remains essential for accuracy and complex queries. By implementing these strategies, the DiSSCo Helpdesk aims to improve user experience, streamline support services, and ensure researchers, collection managers, policymakers, and citizen scientists can effectively utilize DiSSCo's distributed services.

Keywords

DiSSCo Helpdesk, services, self-service resources, user needs

List of abbreviations

BiCIKL (Biodiversity Community Integrated Knowledge Library)

CETAF - Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities

CDD - Collection Digitisation Dashboard

DSR - Digital Specimen Repository

DiSSCo - Distributed System of Scientific Collections

DTP - DiSSCo Transition Project

MNHN - Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle Paris (French National Museum of Natural History)

SLA - Service-Level Agreement

RI - Research Infrastructure

WP - Work Package

UoC - University of Crete

ULisboa - University of Lisbon

1. Introduction

This deliverable provides a plan and framework for the creation and distribution of self-service resources to support users of the DiSSCo Research Infrastructure (RI). These resources will form the first layer of support within the DiSSCo Helpdesk, ensuring that researchers, collection managers, policymakers, educators, and citizen scientists can understand, access, and effectively utilise the distributed services within DiSSCo RI.

This work was conducted under Task 2.3: "Provide entry-point resources for the DiSSCo Helpdesk", led by CETAF, in collaboration with ULisboa and UoC.

1.1. Objective and scope

The primary goal of this task was to develop a self-service structure as the first tier of the DiSSCo Helpdesk system, which is operated by CETAF. This structure is designed to ensure that users can access clear, entry-point resources without requiring immediate assistance from human helpdesk agents. By providing automated and self-service resources, the support system will be streamlined, ensuring that the helpdesk remains efficient and is not overwhelmed with simple, easily resolvable queries.

To achieve this, the task involved gathering feedback from users and service providers regarding:

- Their awareness and understanding of core DiSSCo tools:
 - European Loans and Visits System (ELViS);
 - Collection Digitisation Dashboard (CDD),
 - DiSSCover, and Digital Specimen Repository.
- The types of support they require to fully exploit these services.
- Preferred formats for support materials (e.g., FAQs, tutorials, manuals).

The findings from this process have been used to develop recommendations on the structure, content, and accessibility of support materials. This includes where these resources should be allocated, the workflow for communication within the helpdesk, and strategies for maintaining and updating these resources over time, as well as the responsibility of service providers in this process.

1.2. Background: DiSSCo Helpdesk Structure

The DiSSCo Helpdesk is based on a Jitbit SaaS-hosted system, which was initially set up during the SYNTHESYS+ project. It is designed as a three-tiered support system, providing structured assistance to DiSSCo users:

1st Layer: Self-Service Resources – A collection of tailored resources, including FAQs, tutorials, and written manuals, offering immediate guidance to users.

2nd Layer: Human-Intermediated Q&A – A ticketing system managed by CETAF, where users can submit more complex queries requiring expert assistance.

3rd Layer: Technical Service Level – For queries and Tickets on an IT or data infrastructure level that are too technical for the 2nd layer to handle. This level includes the developers and service providers for technical issues, bug fixes, and advanced troubleshooting.

The primary focus of this deliverable is on the development of the first layer (self-service resources), which serves as the entry point for users seeking assistance.

1.3. Building on Previous EU-Funded Projects

This deliverable builds upon outputs and recommendations from previous EU-funded projects within the DiSSCo ecosystem, including:

- BiCIKL (Biodiversity Community Integrated Knowledge Library) Project – Developed an open biodiversity knowledge hub with tailored training resources.
- [SYNTHESESYS+ Help Desk Guidelines and Workflow](#) – Provided a foundation for structuring the DiSSCo Helpdesk.
- [DiSSCo Prepare Recommendations](#) – Outlined best practices for helpdesk and user support services.
- [DiSSCo Prepare Construction Master Plan](#) – Established strategic goals for infrastructure sustainability and user support.

2. Methodology

To identify the required help resources for core DiSSCo services, CETAF designed and distributed a survey targeting institutions within the DiSSCo National Nodes (NNs). These institutions are expected to be key users of the services. The survey also gathered insights from service providers to understand:

- What types of support users may require.
- Whether existing training materials are available.
- Ideas for the format and structure of new support materials.

The survey was created using Cognito Forms and disseminated through the NNs, who were encouraged to share it with various institutional staff members representing different roles (e.g., researchers, curators, IT support, and collection managers). This ensured a broad and representative response base, capturing diverse perspectives on user needs and support requirements. The survey can be found here: [LINK](#).

3. Survey results

3.1. Overview of survey participation

Overall, the survey received a low response rate, with only 16 individuals from 11 institutions participating. The majority of respondents were Collection Managers, while no feedback was received from potential service providers (**Figure 1**).

The limited response from both DiSSCo users and service providers is likely due to the fact that DiSSCo services are still in development; this was confirmed by 2 participants who mention this in the survey feedback section. Here are some examples of feedback: *“It was somewhat difficult to foresee potential problems and questions that might arise with services that I’m overall not very familiar with.”* and *“Since most of this is experimental or not yet existing, my guess is the real questions to solve will come when these services start working.”* This makes it difficult for users to fully understand the final functionality of these key services and, therefore, their support needs. There are regular demonstrations by the DiSSCo technical team (Naturalis) on the RIs data infrastructure and services like the Digital Specimen Repository and DiSSCover but they are not very well attended. Additionally, at the time of the survey, the hosting responsibilities for some services had not yet been confirmed, which may have further contributed to uncertainty among potential respondents.

Below the results analysis and explanation are provided as different services, addressed separately in the following sections.

Figure 1. Bar chart showing the number of respondents and their different job roles.

3.2. Survey results analysis

Results are presented individually for each service, analysing awareness, understanding, key concerns, and recommended support materials.

3.2.1. Collection Digitisation Dashboard (CDD)

Brief explanation of the service

The interactive dashboard visually summarises the digitisation status, content and strengths of collections across the community of institutions through a number of visual elements. The dashboard provides information both at institutional level and also as an aggregation of all institutions. It displays progress in digitisation and provides summaries and comparisons regarding the number of objects, taxonomic scope, categories of preservation, stratigraphic age, geospatial range, level of digitisation and digital content availability for reuse. **A preview of the pilot dashboard can be found [here](#).**

Survey Results

Figure 2 shows the survey results for the Collection Digitisation Dashboard (CDD). The awareness level is a mixture between high and low. Most of the respondents have a moderate understanding.

The majority of participants (13) suggested that they would need some support for using the tool. Written documentation is the most popular type of support resource, followed by Video tutorials and FAQs.

Key Concerns from questionnaire feedback

- Lack of clarity on how to provide data or connect institutional systems.
- Navigation challenges, with UI elements (e.g., bottom-center navigation bar) being hard to locate.

Recommendations

- Small video - showcasing CDD functional features, navigation and how it can be used.
- Written documentation and FAQs - on data provision (e.g. What standards to use, how to provide the data).
- Improve navigation visibility and include intuitive design elements.
- Only one participant suggested further guidance on Data download; additional graphics.

Collection Digitisation Dashboard

Figure 2. Bar charts showing survey feedback for the Collection Digitisation Dashboard.

3.2.2. ELViS

Brief explanation of the service

ELViS is a one-stop access point to collections in Europe. It provides a unified way to request visits, loans and also virtual access. Virtual access requests through ELViS introduce a new type of access: digitisation on demand. Furthermore, the request mechanism implemented in ELViS also enables future services for tracking usage metrics, monitoring and reporting and connecting collection usage with research outputs.

Survey Results

Awareness and understanding ratings are moderate to high (see Figure 3), though most participants said they lacked familiarity with advanced functionalities. A point to make is that the service description for ELViS, in the survey, contained the link to the old version of ELViS, the new version of ELViS was not available at the time of the survey.

Key Concerns

- Users expressed difficulty understanding the portal's features, such as loan application processes and connecting digital data.
- Requests for best practices and tutorials for handling specific scenarios (e.g., fragile material).

Recommendations

- Written documentation on best practices on how to handle requests from different user role perspectives. For example: Publish guides for handling various use cases, such as fragile material and multi-institution loan requests. Video Tutorials: Develop role-based tutorials covering loan applications, virtual access, and data connections.
- Previously developed help material for the running of the SYNTHESYS+ Transnational Access (TA) and Virtual Access (VA), which used the pilot version of the ELViS platform could be reviewed and updated such as the FAQs. Also with regards to general best practice calls FAQs - some of these could be recycled from the SYNTHESYS+ TA and VA in which the old ELViS was partly used.
- A best practice document for handling material was developed under SYNTHESYS+, but it focused on a particular type of collections ([Policies handbook on using Molecular collections](#)) and did not address specifically the use of ELViS.
- Targeted training and awareness campaigns are needed to improve users' familiarity with ELViS and its functionalities.
- The following recommendations are based on the old ELViS platform but may be useful to consider for the new ELViS platform being built by MNHN Paris:
 - Restructure the introduction: Prioritise clarity for end-users by first stating ELViS's core function before discussing features like tracking metrics and research outputs.

- o Expand the opening description: Include a real-world example of how a researcher might request a loan or virtual access to make it more relatable.
- o Move technical details (Version Info & TRL status): Consider shifting these details to a "Read More" document or separate page to keep the main description user-friendly.
- o Improve accessibility of advanced features: Instead of listing complex functionalities in text form, link to an interactive visual guide for better comprehension.
- o Reduce helpdesk burden: A clearer structure and better presentation of ELViS would help users understand its functionalities more easily, reducing unnecessary support queries.

ELViS survey results

Figure 3.a. Bar charts showing survey feedback for ELViS.

ELViS survey results

Figure 3.b. Bar charts showing survey feedback for ELViS

3.2.3. DiSSCover (Unified Curation and Annotation System)

Brief explanation of the service

[DiSSCover](#) (formerly UCAS) will provide event-based curation and annotation functions on the Digital Specimen for experts in the community and for machines. Transactions on the data will be stored as well as provenance information related to the curation or annotation events.

Key Concerns

- Uncertainty about how to use the service effectively.
- Concerns regarding institutional capacity to manage annotations.

Recommendations

- There should be written manuals/documentation on how to provide and access data.
- Video tutorials on how to access the tool, use the search function and provide data.
- Written best practices and video tutorials on institutional capacity issues, such as staffing and re-digitisation management.

- Publish technical documentation for developers to connect via APIs.
- How to improve the quality of metadata.

DiSSCover survey results

Figure 4. Bar charts showing the survey results for DiSSCover.

3.2.4. Digital Specimen Repository (DSR)

Brief description of service:

The [DSR](#) is a data repository for experimentation with Digital Specimen and other DiSSCo-related FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs).

Results

The majority of respondents rated their awareness of the DSR as low, with most indicating very little familiarity (Figure 5). Only a few demonstrated moderate awareness, and just one reported a high level of awareness. Similarly, understanding of the DSR was predominantly rated as low or moderate, suggesting that while some respondents have a reasonable grasp of its purpose and functions, many still have limited knowledge of its requirements.

During the review of this report, a DiSSCo developer noted that the low awareness and engagement with the DSR might be due to its outdated name. It is more commonly referred to as DSArch (Digital Specimen Architecture), which better reflects its current role. This service is primarily designed for interaction via APIs and other machine agents. Given that most respondents were collection managers, their lack of familiarity is understandable, as they are not the primary target audience for this service. It was also considered that the survey results from the DSR and DiSSCover should be merged since the DSR is the back-end to DiSSCover.

Key Concerns

- Lack of understanding about the potential applications and purpose of the DSR.
- Limited knowledge about how to submit data to the platform.
- Challenges in managing user access requests through the DSR at institutional levels.
- General unawareness of existing or planned guidance materials.

Recommendations

- Develop tutorials with step-by-step instructions for navigating the DSR and performing key tasks such as data submission and managing access requests.
- Provide comprehensive written documentation as the primary resource, supplemented by video tutorials and FAQs.
- Host live demonstrations or webinars to introduce users to the DSR and its functionalities.
- Create tailored materials that address common use cases and different user roles.

DSR survey results

Figure 5. Bar charts showing the survey results for the DSR.

4. Self-Service Resource and first-layer helpdesk recommendations

This section provides general recommendations on the development of self-service resources and outlines how the first layer of the helpdesk, managed by CETAF, will facilitate continuous communication between service providers and the helpdesk. This will ensure that materials are regularly updated and further developed based on user

needs. Self-service resources will be developed by service providers in coordination with CETAF, who will ensure that user needs are channelled to those service providers.

4.1 Self-service material development and allocation

- Adopt a user-centred development approach to ensure support materials are structured around real user needs.
- Implement role-specific support materials tailored to different user types (e.g. researchers, curators and technical staff).
- The survey feedback suggests that users still demand easy access options for human help.
- Centralise all support resources in one location, in a dedicated help page within each service to provide a streamlined user experience.
- Ensure support materials are also available via, or linked to, the DiSSCo knowledge hub.
- Include basic information on the DiSSCo website to raise awareness and understanding of services.
- Given the low to moderate awareness of services, ensure each service includes:
 - A clear “About” page explaining its purpose and functionality.
 - A dedicated help page or resource hub with links to video tutorials, written documentation, FAQs and the helpdesk email.
- Recognise that training resources are challenging to define while services are still in development:
 - The Helpdesk hosts (CETAF) should engage with service providers to develop necessary support materials based on these recommendations.
 - Conduct regular performance evaluations to assess the effectiveness of the helpdesk and its resources, ensuring they continue to meet the user needs. This could be done as a short feedback survey.

4.2 Helpdesk-Service interactions and Service Level Agreements (SLAs)

It is recommended that the following is included into the DiSSCo service SLAs:

- Service hosts regularly review and update documentation, FAQs, and training materials to reflect changes or improvement.
- Service hosts work periodically with the help desk hosts to analyse support tickets and recurring users queries to identify gaps in existing resources. Develop new content where needed to proactively address common issues and reduce repeat queries.
- For queries that cannot be resolved via existing support materials or first-line helpdesk support, service providers should offer technical support to ensure timely and accurate responses.

- Close collaboration between the helpdesk and service providers is essential for maintaining an effective and responsive user support system.

Figure 6 illustrates the proposed workflow between the helpdesk and services.

Figure 6. Proposed Workflow Between the DiSSCo Helpdesk and Service Providers. This diagram outlines the step-by-step communication workflow, labelled 1 to 4, illustrating how users engage with the helpdesk system. It begins with users searching the service help pages for self-service resources. If further assistance is needed, queries are directed to the helpdesk, which then relays information between users and service providers.

4.3 Exploration of AI Integration for the DiSSCo Helpdesk

Given DiSSCo's diverse user base and CETAF's limited staff capacity, AI-powered support could enhance efficiency, scalability, and multilingual accessibility. AI-driven chatbots can provide instant, 24/7 support, reducing pressure on human staff by directing users to relevant FAQs and documentation. They enable natural language queries, refine FAQs based on user interactions, and identify documentation gaps ([Proprofsdesks.com](https://proprofsdesks.com)). AI can also anticipate user needs and cross-reference external research helpdesks (e.g., EOSC) for broader support.

4.3.1 Key Considerations for AI Implementation

- AI must comply with GDPR and Open Science principles to ensure responsible data handling.
- AI-generated responses rely on pre-existing data and may occasionally produce inaccurate or outdated information.

- Human validation remains essential to monitor AI-generated content and maintain response quality.
- Complex technical queries should still be handled by human experts, as AI lacks the emotional intelligence to detect user frustration or communication difficulties.
- The chatbot should have an option for escalation to technical experts when users require detailed assistance beyond automated responses.
- AI should be introduced incrementally, with user feedback loops in place to refine and improve functionality.
- Implementing a user rating system for AI responses will help assess effectiveness and guide improvements.
- Deploying AI features requires investment in software, integration, and staff training to ensure a smooth transition.
- AI should be continuously updated to reflect changes in services and evolving user needs.
- Users should be clearly informed when interacting with AI and given the option to request human support when necessary.
- AI should enhance, rather than replace, human-led support services, ensuring that users always have access to expert guidance when needed.

The [litbit SaaS Helpdesk](#) includes built-in AI capabilities through ChatGPT integration, although it appears to come at a cost. Key features include:

- Automated response suggestions based on the knowledge base.
- Smart search recommendations to direct users to relevant resources.
- Ticket summarisation for quicker handling by support agents.
- Automated refinement of agent responses to improve clarity and consistency.

5. Conclusion

The development of a structured, self-service training resource model for the DiSSCo Helpdesk is crucial for enhancing user accessibility and support within the DiSSCo RI. The findings highlight key gaps in user awareness and engagement with core DiSSCo services, such as ELViS, CDD, DiSSCover, and the Digital Specimen Repository (DSR). Addressing these gaps requires a well-defined support structure that prioritizes clarity, accessibility, and sustainability.

A first-tier self-service model is essential to provide immediate assistance to users. To achieve this, documentation, FAQs, and video tutorials should be centralized on dedicated help pages for each service. Additionally, role-based learning materials should be developed to cater to researchers, curators, technical staff and policymakers, ensuring that each user group has access to relevant and understandable support resources.

Sustaining and improving these resources will require continuous collaboration between the helpdesk, service providers and users. A feedback loop should be established to ensure that resources remain relevant and up to date, addressing user needs as they evolve. Service providers must play an active role in updating and refining support

materials based on user queries and system changes. Additionally, periodic user surveys should be conducted to assess helpdesk performance and identify areas for improvement.

To enhance efficiency, the report explores the potential integration of AI-powered chatbots and automated knowledge retrieval systems. These tools can handle routine inquiries, direct users to relevant resources, and reduce the burden on human helpdesk agents. However, AI should be implemented as a complementary tool rather than a replacement for human-led support, particularly for complex technical issues. AI-generated responses must be monitored for accuracy, and users should always have the option to escalate their queries to a human expert when necessary. Furthermore, AI implementations must comply with GDPR regulations to ensure ethical data handling and privacy protection.

Since DiSSCo Services are still evolving, the helpdesk framework should be designed with scalability in mind. Training resources and support materials must remain flexible to accommodate new services and updates. Raising user awareness through targeted outreach efforts and training sessions can further improve engagement with DiSSCo's digital tools. By implementing these strategies, the DiSSCo Helpdesk will become a robust, scalable, and user-centric support system, ensuring that researchers, collection managers, policymakers and citizen scientists can seamlessly interact with and benefit from DiSSCo's distributed services.

6. Acknowledgments

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